

EVILINHD, a Virtual Research Environment open and collaborative for DH Scholars

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Virtual Research Environments (VREs) have become central objects for digital humanist community, as they help global, interdisciplinary and networked research taking of profit of the changes in “data production, curation and (re-)use, by new scientific methods, by changes in technology supply” (Voss and Procter, 2009: 174-190). DH Centers, labs or less formal structures such as associations benefit from many kinds of VREs, as they facilitate researchers and users a place to develop, store, share and preserve their work, making it more visible. The focus and implementation of each of these VREs is different, as Carusi and Reimer (2010) show in their comparative analysis, but there are some common guidelines, philosophy and standards that are generally shared (as an example, see the Centernet map and guidelines of TGIR Huma-Num 2015).

This lighting talk presents the structure and design of the VRE of LINHD, the Digital Innovation Lab at UNED (<http://linhd.uned.es>), and the first Digital Humanities Center in Spain. EVILINHD focuses on the possibilities of a collaborative environment for (profane or advanced) DH Scholars.

The platform developed offers a bilingual English-Spanish interface that allows users register, create new projects and join the existing ones. Projects are shared by teams and created and published from the beginning to the final publication on the web without exiting the platform. Three types of projects may be created: 1) digital scholarly TEI-based editions using eXistDB, TEIScribe and TEIPublisher, 2) digital libraries using Omeka, and 3) simple and beautiful websites using Wordpress. There is also a customized option which allows to create projects combining all of these ingredients or part of them.

Once projects are finished, the environment offers the possibility of publication in LINDAT repository, the Clarin.eu infrastructure for deposit data and projects, as LINHD is part of the Spanish Clarin-K Centre (Bel, González-Blanco and Iruskieta, forthcoming). To publish projects into the repository, additional metadata are requested following the TADIRAH DH classification created by DARIAH. Once projects are published in LINDAT, they get permanent identifiers provided by Handle and they are harvested by the Clarin.eu Virtual Language Observatory.

The environment combines open-access free software tools well-known and widespread in the DH communities, and also some proprietary developments, like the TEIScribe visual XML cloud editor, developed at LINHD. All of them are integrated in a single log on environment based on Ubuntu and covered with an architecture of web standard technologies (such as PHP, SQL, Python and eXistDB).

Bibliographical references

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